

DYSTOPIC REALITY IN THE UTOPIAN DREAM IN 1984 AND A CLOCKWORK ORANGE**1984 VE OTOMATİK PORTAKAL ESERLERİNDE ÜTOPIK HAYAL İÇERİSİNDEKİ DİSTOPIK GERÇEKLİK****Edanur ZENGİN**

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Abstract

The reflections of the two great world wars, which continue to affect their effects socially, psychologically and economically, are among the issues that should not be overlooked in literature. It is also known that many troubles that broke out especially after the Second World War caused great destruction to individuals. In particular, the destruction of individuals in the modern period has been the subject of utopian or dystopian works by many authors in terms of both criticizing existing governments or social orders and giving many recommendations and warnings for the future. George Orwell's *1984* and Anthony Burgess' *A Clockwork Orange* are also among dystopian works. Based on the idea that dystopian and utopian worldviews are accepted subjectively, it is possible to state that both works are also utopian world descriptions. In this study, the transformation of the world order, which is accepted as utopian for society in *1984* and *A Clockwork Orange*, into a dystopia for individuals will be discussed. The purpose of this article is to criticize that the uniform human model, which was tried to be created by governments in the post-war period, caused mechanization and enslavement. This policy of mechanization has positive causes and implications for governments. However, for individuals who seek to exist in society, being a robot means both abstracting individuals from the broad outlines of society and normalizing a murder against their humanity. From this perspective, in George Orwell's *1984* novel, the thoughts of individuals are blocked by formations such as the Thought Police. On the other hand, in Anthony Burgess' *A Clockwork Orange*, human desires within the individual are attempted to be silenced and destroyed. This world order, which is tried to be created for the principal characters created to reflect many disorders as symbols of society, is transformed into a dystopia. As a consequence of this article, the idea that any utopia is someone else's dystopia will be inferred.

Keywords: Utopia, Dystopia, George Orwell, Anthony Burgess, *1984*, *A Clockwork Orange*, Enslavement, Mechanization.

Öz

Günümüzde etkilerini sosyal, psikolojik, ekonomik yönden etkilemeye devam eden iki büyük dünya savaşının edebiyata yansımaları gözden kaçırılmaması gereken hususlar arasındadır. Özellikle İkinci Dünya Savaşı sonrasında patlak veren birçok sorunun devamında bireyler üzerinde oldukça büyük yıkımlara sebep olduğu da bilinmektedir. Özellikle modern dönemdeki bireylerin sahip olduğu yıkımlar hem var olan hükümetleri ya da toplum düzenlerini eleştirmek hem de geleceğe yönelik birçok tavsiye ve uyarı bildirmek açısından birçok yazar tarafından ütöpik ya da distöpik eserlere konu olmaktadır. George Orwell'ın *1984* ve Anthony Burgess'ın *Otomatik Portakal* eserleri de distöpik eserler arasında yer almaktadır. Distöpik ve ütöpik dünya görüşlerinin subjektif olarak kabul edildiği düşüncesinden hareketle iki eserinde aynı zamanda ütöpik dünya tasvirleri olduğunu belirtmek mümkündür. Bu çalışmada *1984* ve *Otomatik Portakal* eserleri toplum için ütöpik olarak kabul edilen dünya düzeninin bireyler için birer distopyaya dönüşümü ele alınacaktır. Bu makalenin amacı savaş sonrası dönemde hükümetler tarafından yaratılmaya çalışılan tek tip insan modelinin makineleştirilmeye ve köleleştirmeye sebep olduğunu eleştirmektir. Bu makineleştirilme politikası hükümetler açısından olumlu sebep ve sonuçlar içermektedir. Ancak bununla birlikte toplumda var olmaya çalışan bireyler için bir robotlaştırılmak hem bireyleri toplumun ana hatlarından soyutlamak hem de insanlıklarına karşı yapılan bir cinayeti

normalleştirmek anlamlarına gelmektedir. Bu açıdan bakıldığında George Orwell'ın 1984 adlı romanında bireylerin düşünceleri Düşünce Polisi gibi oluşumlar tarafından engellenmektedir. Diğer bir yandan Anthony Burgess tarafından yazılan *Otomatik Portakal* adlı eserde de bireyin içerisindeki insani istekler susturulmaya ve tamamen yok edilmeye çalışılmaktadır. Toplumun birer sembolü olarak birçok sıkıntıyı yansıtmak amacıyla yaratılan ana karakterler için var edilmeye çalışılan bu dünya düzeni bir distopyaya dönüşmektedir. Bu makale sonucunda her ütopyanın bir başkasının distopyası olduğu düşüncesi çıkarılacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Ütopya, Distopya, George Orwell, Anthony Burgess, 1984, *Otomatik Portakal*, Köleleştirilme, Makineleştirilme.

Introduction

The pursuit of power and a prosperous life expectancy that started after the geographical discoveries pushed the states towards the colonial system that has been going on for centuries. With the colonial system, some states argued that they were superior to other states, either in color or regional. In accordance with the profits of the church, defending these states against other weak states also laid the groundwork for the slavery system that emerged after colonialism. The Church counseled these people that they must obey throughout their lives as slaves to be forgiven for their sinfulness. That is also mentioned in the 1984's characters that had to be slaves in order to attain their freedom in heaven, 'Slavery is freedom' can be considered as a source of expression. As a result, people became more attached to the colonial system over time and laid the groundwork for world wars, the effects of which still continue today. After these wars, different systems applied to the public by various governments around the world have occurred. The purpose of these systems, which caused deep destruction to individuals in many economic, social, and psychological issues, was to provide order in society within the specified frameworks by creating a uniform human model. This is known as the utopian world description that various states such as the USSR and Germany are trying to establish.

“Utopias are the products of reaching the idealist from the realist. It means ‘Utopia of Fear’ Dystopia, on the other hand, deals with the vision of a distorted society, not the conception of an ideal society.”(Avcı, 2021, p. 193). As it can be understood from the definition given, utopia aims to establish a good society. Utopian works aim to shape and mechanize individuals in a certain framework. On the other hand, dystopia, even if it is not the opposite of utopia completely, opposes the mechanization of people and argues that individuals cannot conform to a uniform human model. The principle of perfection that the utopias want to establish also includes the slavery system. “The other interesting thing about dystopia is that democracy, science and socialism have become the forces that prepare hell in dystopia, which are the source of hope for utopia.”(Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 181). The established form of society has to remain as created by the governments, and this puts an endless inhibition on freedom. This dictatorship system established by governments causes various effects such as alienation, isolation and loss of self in the society. As a result, some individuals, even though they are considered to be in the minority, start to rebel, aiming to get rid of this wheel and regain their free will by entering into hope. The social order depicted as utopian turns into a dystopia for individuals. In short, utopian worlds that are tried to be established by governments due to the will to power are dystopias as terrible as a nightmare for individuals.

“In a sense, as part of the first person's destiny, there is a search for paradise lost in almost every period of the historical process... the dystopian society created by the effects of millions of people's deaths and terrifying marginal ideologies have also been established.”(Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 179).

The main aim of utopian and dystopian novels is to criticize the oppressive policies of the existing governments and the totalitarian regime through the stories created. "Given these examples, it is possible to say that a similar assessment of utopian literature applies to dystopian literature and that the problems posed by existing political structures constitute a source for writing such works." (Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 180). Especially in the 20th century, with technological developments, it is easier for governments to control rights. However, various forms of colonialism such as communism and capitalism are also becoming widespread. The idea that freedom consists of slavery is an attempt to take away the thinking function of the people. As a result, free will is attempted to be destroyed. This is a goal of the utopian world. However, it is an undeniable fact that these social systems, in which the idea that utopia can change from individual to individual, is seen as a dystopia for some individuals. So, every established utopia is also a dystopia. "Utopias inspire hope, dystopias inspire pessimism." (Avcı, 2021, p. 194). A world order that may be considered good for one individual may be a bad depiction that may be considered a nightmare for another individual or society. At the same time, the world order that is accepted as orderly for a society can be complex and chaotic for individuals.

The novel *1984*, written in 1949 by George Orwell, who wrote political works such as *Animal Farm*, is also considered a dystopian and political novel. The novel, which aims to criticize the regimes such as Nazism, Communism, and Capitalism put forward by the governments after the Second World War, also criticizes their acceptance by the people without questioning their thoughts. In addition, he discusses that the regimes were questioned by some minority individuals and caused various uprisings. The novel, which aims to reveal the dictatorial ideas accepted without question, is about individuals like Winston Smith who are enslaved. Winston, who lives in the Oceania region, is the main character of the novel who opposes the system created by the government. He cannot share his thoughts with anyone because even having opinions against the system is considered a crime. The punishment for this crime is to be destroyed by evaporation. The purpose of Orwell, which includes the concept of evaporation without using the concept of death, is a reference to the Jews who were incinerated in the Nazi camp. Orwell aims to not forget such events and to question them for criticizing this injustice done by Germany. Winston, on the other hand, is one of the party members who destroys the news about the past or changes them as the party orders. He begins to write down his negative thoughts about Big Brother, who is at the head of the party and who allegedly watches and sees everything, in a diary that he bought from an antique store. This is how he starts his anti-party period in this period when even writing is prohibited, and in the meantime begins to question his job. Everything except eating, working and sleeping is prohibited by the party. Meanwhile, he starts a forbidden union with Julia and breaks the principle of living together without the knowledge of the party by falling in love which the party has forbidden. O'Brien, who initially seemed to be on the same front as Winston, is a member of the 'brotherhood' group against Big Brother. He delivers the book written by Emmanuel Goldstein to Winston. He reads this book aloud to Julia at the antique shop but realizes that he cannot find anything that he doesn't know. They get caught on the party side. As a result of various tortures applied by the party, Winston turns into an individual who has been brainwashed and lost his free will. When confronted with his fear of mice, which he has repeated since the beginning of the novel, he betrays even Julia and demands that this torture be done to Julia. Winston, who started to like Big Brother at the end of the novel, gave in to the party despite all his rebellion, because the party preferred to brainwash the individuals who opposed them rather than kill them. Winston has now become a robot and continues to live like a slave as a supporter of the party. This novel handles the transformation of the utopian world established by the party into a dystopian world depicted by individuals.

A dystopian work like the 1984 novel *A Clockwork Orange*, written by Anthony Burgess in 1962, contains various criticisms of the governments that existed after the Second World War. In addition, it contains warnings that the uniform human model, which is trying to be created by violence with the effort of giving messages for the future, will create a violent society by having more violence. In a society where there is violence, sociopathic young people's opposition to society with greater violence causes violence that cannot be prevented. The government, which is thought to be utopian, applies to Alex a Ludovico Technique by making criminal individuals watch violent films in order to prevent violent situations such as murder, harassment, and rape. 15-year-old Alex is the gang leader who is a student by day and a nightmare at night. This gang, including George, Tim and Pete, are characters created to criticize the government. On the other hand, the work, which contains messages for a future full of violence, deals with the results of the changes that started with modernization in the 1960s. Alex, who is different from the usual protagonists and has a Robin Hood style, is the only child of a humble family where violence does not exist. "There has to be a leader. Discipline there has to be." (Burgess, 2011, p. 22). His parents go to work early in the morning while he sleeps. This calmness is actually a reference to individuals who submit to society. On the other hand, the parents who go to work early and cannot spare enough time for their children are a reflection of the working class existing in society and the individuals who have to work all the time. As it can be comprehended from the title of the novel, the society that demands mechanization, enslavement and automation is stereotyped within a uniform human model.

"Uniform human fiction is the most important subject of dystopian novels. As a result of the abuse of technology, people are forced into a single type by the dominant ruling power, their differences are eroded, there is no place for any 'human' situation out of control with overwhelming domination, the logic of crime and punishment is based on not losing control of the system. almost impossible to make is enough for an opinion about dystopias." (Avci, 2021, p. 194).

In particular, individuals who return to their homes like innocent individuals after the torture they inflict on women, the elderly and children are individuals stuck in two separate utopian worlds. After the Second World War, these 15-year-old individuals cannot live without violence. They break into the house of the author of *A Clockwork Orange* and criticize the violence in society, beat the author and rape his wife in front of his eyes. After this incident, the gang returns to the house of an old woman living with her cats, causing her death. Alex is ambushed by other members of the gang and the vandal gang escapes, but Alex is caught by the police. Alex, who has to undergo an experiment in which individuals with very serious crimes are tried to be turned into normal individuals by the government, is accepted in return for the removal of 14 years of imprisonment. For a while, various inhumane films with violent content are watched and classical music is played here, along with various narcotic drugs.

One of his favorite things is to listen to the classical music of artists such as Ludwig van and Alex's pleasure is considered as a dimension of violence. Alex is also sensitive to violence and blood for sensitizing by Pavlovian experiments with music. Many things have changed as Alex's gang mates. He is beaten by his friends and thrown out of town. Finally, he takes refuge in the author's house and asks him for help. The writer realizes that he is the leader of the gang and Alex wants to commit suicide because of this. At the end of the novel, Alex no longer feels the effects of the experiment. The protagonist, who was created with a very bad personality, actually reflects the free will and the choice to be a good or bad individual.

“Alex is actually a good person; what he is trying to realize is to prove that no choice can be imposed over him. In other words, if Alex was imposed to choose the bad over the good he would have probably chosen the good this time; to him, it is not a matter of good or bad, it is a matter of freedom.”(Tuncer, 2019, pp. 72-73).

This proves the idea that robotized individuals accept the utopian world established by society as a dystopia. “In secularizing these views of man, we tend to forget about sin and concentrate on what is good for society and what is not.”(Burgess, 2011, p. 158).

1. Conversion of the Utopian World into Dystopia in 1984

1984 deals with individuals who are trying to be shaped as the ideal social order to criticize various regimes initiated by governments in the post-war period. In this way, it emphasizes themes such as social justice and equality. "Orwell, who is also a Socialist, in this work; what has happened, especially the power elites, their desire to design or intervene, their ambitions to manage, individual and criticized the attempts to dominate the society."(Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 181). On the other hand, it is emphasized that the uniform human model through fear, tyranny and oppression is not a utopia but a dystopian life for individuals. As can be comprehended from these expressions, various world systems designed especially with the colonial system take away the questioning and thinking power of individuals, causing oppressive systems in which there is no free will. These individuals, who are turned into slaves, are forced to live in the order created by erasing the past from their brains in desperation. This dictatorship system is a utopian world that deprives individuals of all their rights except for eating, working and sleeping. Big Brother owns this utopia and is all-knowing.

The Party found some systems such as 'Thought Police' which monitors the thoughts of individuals, and also examines whether the public has any bad perceptions towards the party. "This fear is so ingrained in people in 1984 that breaking the party's rules, not just breaking it. They can't even think of it. And that's why thinking is a crime."(Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 183). This government, which is trying to be reflected as utopian, continues to press for the internalization of three statements, which are the main rules. "War is peace. Freedom is slavery. Ignorance is strength."(Orwell, 2000, p. 7). Individuals who oppose these statements, such as Winston, are arrested by the Thought Police. Individuals are brainwashed by various tortures and techniques, and the party's principles are tried to be imposed. Individuals who resist it are vaporized. The purpose of the evaporation process is to erase the rebellious individuals as if they did not exist and to protect the future of the party.

Winston is one of the party members tasked with destroying the anti-Party actions in the papers and the news and changing them in favor of the Party.

"Before it produces a fake event that happened in the past, then broadcasts it. Then, by changing all the records in the archive, the event gives the impression that it is. There is only one thing left to disprove; individuals' memories. This too takes place by destroying language."(Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 185).

In this period, when it is known that language mediates thought, another action taken besides erasing the past is to ensure that new principles such as 'Doublethink' or 'Newspeak' are accepted by individuals. Thanks to these techniques, it is aimed to prevent behaviors and thoughts against the party. Free thought is forbidden in this society where Tele Screens and microphones are everywhere. "In reality there was no escape."(Orwell, 2000, p. 138). Various advances made by technology open the door to a dystopian world. This order is considered dystopia by individuals because this non-chaotic system contains many concepts such as mechanization, political power, inequality, and totalitarianism. These dictatorial systems do

not allow any privacy or free will. "Orwell clearly underlines that there is no place for humans in such a world, it is no longer humans but puppets that do as they are told." (Müftüoğlu, 2015, p. 183). Winston thinks that he is one of the members of the secret society called Brotherhood by Emmanuel Goldstein. For this reason, he records all the troubles he sees in his diary in order not to forget and to warn the future. Winston aims to isolate himself from the Tele Screen at home by performing this action in the blind spot of his home. This reflects that the system established for people who do not have a secret life, even at home, is a dystopia.

Winston and Julia, who create a secret utopia in the upstairs room of the antique shop, make conversations against the party, but she falls asleep. This is a reflection of individuals put to sleep by the government. O'Brien is a friend of Winston's workplace. O'Brien follows Winston to the antique shop. He says that he is against the party as well and that he is in the structure called 'Brotherhood', which aims to destroy the party by immediately starting an uprising. He invites Julia and Winston to his house to find out if they are part of this secret society. The utopian couple who accept this offer receive from O'Brien the book *Against the Party* and published by Emmanuel Goldstein. When he reads the book aloud in the antique shop room, Winston realizes that the book does not contain any new information. "History has stopped. Nothing exists except an endless present in which the Party is always right." (Orwell, 2000, p. 141). In the morning, the shop is surrounded by the Thought Police, as evidenced by the sound reflects on the Tele Screen behind a picture hanging in the room. O'Brien and the shop owner, Mr. Charrington are also found to be agents of the party. Winston and Julia, who are arrested after all these situations that turn into a dystopian world, are subjected to various brainwashing tortures.

"What distinguishes both the psychological and physical methods of torture is that they are aimed at achieving one goal, denying Winston the ability to write or think, as they are closely related; writing comes as a process resulting from thinking, awareness and perception." (Talalweh, 2022, p. 52).

Although O'Brien does not achieve this completely, he can to some extent shape his thoughts in favor of the party. "We do not merely destroy our enemies, we change them." (Orwell, 2000, p. 229). This is another illustration for dystopia. His fear of mice expresses the idea that no fear should be told in society. Because the fears voiced are used by the utopian society. He has never betrayed Julia since the beginning of his arrest, but he surrenders to the utopian world that has turned into a dystopia because of this fear. "I do not care what you do to her. Tear her face off, strip her to the bones. Not me! Julia! Not me!" (Orwell, 2000, p. 259). As a result, he is released. When he encounters Julia, Winston feels nothing against her because he has been mechanized by utopia. "He finally realizes that the victory over himself is complete and sees how useless it was to resist." (Orwell, 2000, p. 329).

All the events that integrate the novel *1984* from the beginning to the end aim to emphasize the subject that the utopian or dystopian world can change from person to person. The world design that is utopian for one individual can turn into a nightmare and dystopia for another individual. Someone's dream is someone's nightmare. In fact, every utopia is also a dystopia, and every dystopia is a utopia. As it can be understood from these expressions George Orwell states that the utopian world plans that took place after the war are actually a ruse and deception.

"Monopolize a country's political and military power inevitably, in order to maintain and preserve this regime, while establishing a uniform life order is the main theme of the novel, this order the planning and execution of murders that are justified to establish oppression and control of citizens for fear of arrest are at the center of criticism." (Uysal, 2012, p. 141).

In addition, the author aims to prove that utopias can turn into dystopias for people through the characters Winston and Julia by emphasizing the impossibility of a utopian world.

2. Conversion of Utopian World into Dystopia in *A Clockwork Orange*

A Clockwork Orange by Anthony Burgess, which contains messages containing various warnings for the future, refers to many pressures in society.

“And if the novella at the centre of the book must be judged a let down by Burgess’s best standards, 1985 deserves attention for its wide-ranging political and social discussions, for the Orwellian pastiche of its note on ‘Worker’s English’, and, above all, for its reassessments of that most powerful of modern cacotopias, Nineteen Eighty-Four.”(Parrinder, 2011, p. 265).

This novel criticizes the government because more violence is caused, and the idea that free will does not exist and people are turned into machines.

“The root of the dystopia in the first section is ultra-violence, and that of the second is the state’s repressive tactics on man, that is, a sanctioned violence aiming at discarding violence from the society through the tactics that dehumanize man through depriving him of his free will.”(Zengin, 2015, pp. 93-94).

It makes the reader think about the isolation of a vandalizing gang with various crimes such as rape, torture, harassment and murder, and the reasons for their inclination to violence. Alex's personality, which is different from the known protagonists, suggests that individuals were actually pushed to violence by society in the post-war period. "...things changing so sorry these days and everybody very quick to forget, newspapers not being read much neither.”(Burgess, 2011, p. 3). Sociopaths Alex, George, Dim and Pete look like ordinary students during the day and become a nightmare for the public at night. The utopian world that exists during the day is a dystopia for them. That's why the gang, who are against the daily life where free thought does not exist, establish their utopia at night. However, this utopia is interpreted as a dystopia for many remaining individuals. Alex does not actually choose to be a bad individual, his trouble is not to be 'good' or 'bad', but to have free will.

“The day was very different from the night. The night belonged to me and my droogs and all the rests of the nadsats, and the starry bourgeois lurked indoors drinking in the gloppy worldcasts, but the day was for the starry ones, and there always seemed to be more rozzes or millicents about during the day too.”(Burgess, 2011, p. 30).

For this reason, the main character, who is deprived of his freedom during the day, turns into a monster at night and becomes the dystopia of society. It can be comprehended from these expressions that the utopian and dystopian world is an individual thought.

Alex grew up in a house where there is no domestic violence and is the only child of the family. From the outside, there is no reason for him to participate in violent acts. However, sometimes a world where everything is normal can create abnormal and devastating consequences. This situation can be considered related to the character of the individual. Normality can be called utopia, while abnormality can be considered dystopia. Alex, who cannot keep up with the utopian order at home, opposes the system and prefers to build his own utopia against this order, which has turned into a dystopia for himself. He chooses to have free will in his own violent world, rather than being good in a world where choices do not matter.

“Seen from Alex’s viewpoint the situation becomes dystopia but viewed from the lens of the government it constitutes utopian elements. While the government has a utopian desire/aspiration, the case becomes a dystopia for its people. The situation is clear

enough: One's utopia may be the other's dystopia; one's dream may become a nightmare for the other."(Zengin, 2015, p. 94).

Alex's life is filled with pressure from an educational counselor because of his previous crimes. In a conversation with his father, he lies and reproaches his father, stating that he does errands at night. His father does not object to this, because the father figure in the book is actually a symbol of individuals who remain silent against dictatorial governments. Alex does not explain this to his father and expresses that he does not want money from him, so he is free. He thinks that he has the right to act completely independently of his family, claiming that he has economic freedom. This can be explained by the longing for freedom in the established utopian life.

Besides violence, Alex is also obsessed as a sociopath with classical music. Especially Ludwig van, who he likes to listen to, completely passes out during music and is isolated from life. Meanwhile, the only thought that exists in the fantasy world is violence. This fantasy world, where violence is integrated with classical music, is thought to be the only area where Alex feels free. With these characters, Anthony Burgess aims to emphasize that the cruel utopian order created by society has thoughts that are unbearable and can lead to worse results. "Violence makes violence."(Burgess, 2011, p. 47).

The part that can be considered as the turning point of all their violent nights is the evening they entered the house of the author who wrote the work '*A Clockwork Orange*'. His work *A Clockwork Orange* contains real-life stories with many themes of violence. It is a utopia that causes violence within the established system. The gang, who find this work quite ridiculous, starts beating the writer. During this violence, the drops of blood splashing on the papers and around make the gang very blessed. Because the author aims to establish also includes a separate utopia. "The government's utopian desire to eliminate violence turns into a kind of suppression because the government's tool is violence."(Zengin, 2015, p. 100). However, they cannot digest this situation and go further and rape the wife of the dying writer in front of his eyes as they are blindly attached to their own utopia. This is considered one of the most unbearable parts of the novel. Many readers felt like they were in a nightmare in this part of the novel. This is the reader's dystopia as well. Burgess aims to claim that each individual's utopia can be different.

"In his novel titled *A Clockwork Orange* set soon Burgess expresses his predictions about the troubles the West will face in the future and foresees that these troubles will bring the end of civilization if the West does not take necessary precautions."(Eren, 2018, p. 145).

The same night, the gang, who broke into the house of an old woman living with her cats, beat her mercilessly. Alex is caught by the police for murder after falling into the trap set by the gang group. Even the utopia created by Alex and his friends has turned into a dystopia for his friends over time. "There was no trust anywhere in the world."(Burgess, 2011, p. 60). Every individual wants to be the leader of the utopia he has established, so individuals may encounter such deceptions. Alex is subjected to a newly found experiment by the government. This experiment takes place against Alex's will. "...nowadays were being turned into machines."(Burgess, 2011, p. 102). This is a post about people being enslaved.

Violent films are shown to Alex through the method called 'Lucovico Technique' in order to end his tendency towards violence. These films become more unbearable with the drugs given. During these movies about war, rape and murder, Alex is tied to a chair and is not allowed to take his eyes off it for a second. Alex, who is a fan of classical music, is played

his favorite music during a movie. "Stop the film! Please, please stop it! I cannot stand anymore."(Burgess, 2011, p. 71). Alex objects to it being taken away, saying that music is the only reality he clings to. But music is used more. This technique is necessary for the utopian world that Alex has built within himself to turn into a dystopia. Alex is released after the experiment. He returns to his free life and is beaten by his friends and thrown out of the city. He cannot stand violence and wants to commit suicide. Because instead of the utopia he has established, he finds himself on a completely different adventure and cannot keep up with it. After a while, the effects of the experiment fade from day to day. His self is not as intense as he used to be. And this is due to the fact that a part of his self submits to the utopia in society.

"What is humane and virtuous is man's distinguishing between the good and the bad, and the operation of his moral choice to prefer the good or the bad. Human beings are inherently good and are endowed with the free will that can be engendered if man is not dehumanized by the other forces, and he would not become a clockwork orange insofar as he is permitted to conserve his moral compass."(Zengin, 2015, p. 101).

It is seen that people are robotized by the government and a uniform human model is aimed through *A Clockwork Orange*. "I think that you can help dislodge this overbearing Government. To turn a decent young man into a piece of clockwork should not, surely, be seen as any triumph for any government, save one that boasts of its repressiveness."(Burgess, 2011, p. 100). It is emphasized that each individual's utopia is different and that utopias contain the self-thoughts of individuals, through the main hero named Alex, who fights against the created utopia.

Conclusion

It is known that after the two great wars that took place in the world with the colonial system, governments established different regimes and thus tried to establish a social order. As a result, throughout history, every government has tried to establish its own utopia. Governments, whose main purpose is to establish a better society in order, have been the subject of many dystopian works in the 20th century. George Orwell's *1984* and Anthony Burgess's *A Clockwork Orange* are among the most important of these works. Various criticisms conveyed by Winston Smith and Alex emphasize that the utopian world is a subjective idea.

"Utopia wants to offer us this perfection. It only expects us to meet basic needs such as food, drink and reproduction, and ignore genuine human feelings such as thinking. Dystopia is exactly a critique of this. While utopia asks us to be like machines, dystopia asks us to return to being human. In these contexts, Claeys says, "One's utopia is another's dystopia." The word sounds quite logical." (Çağlayan, 2021)

This article claims that utopias are subjective through the statements given. The purpose of this article, which examines *1984* and *A Clockwork Orange*, states that governments enslave people. In addition, it is aimed to reveal the idea that the works that are a reaction to totalitarianism will carry society to a much worse position. In this article, the works titled *1984* and *A Clockwork Orange* contain that the utopian world can turn into a dystopian world and that a uniform human model is not possible.

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